

Studies on Oxidation. Part IV. Action of Ferric Chloride and Hydrogen Peroxide on *S*-Alkyl thiosemicarbazones : Formation of Triazoles.

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In Part I of this series (De and Roy-Choudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 269) the oxidation of some thiosemicarbazones to thiodiazole or triazole derivatives has been described. In the present communication, the oxidation of *S*-alkyl thiosemicarbazones of aldehydes by means of ferric chloride and hydrogen peroxide is described. Since there are only two reactive hydrogen atoms in the molecule, and not three as in the case of an aldehyde thiosemicarbazone, the possibility of formation of thiodiazoles is totally excluded. The reaction therefore leads to triazoles irrespective of the nature of oxidising agents employed, which, in the case of aldehyde thiosemicarbazones, appear to have a selective action (Part I, p. 270).

The yields of the products, when ferric chloride was employed, were invariably poor, due evidently to the decomposition of the molecule. With *S*-alkyl benzylidene thiosemicarbazones no definite product could be separated. With hydrogen peroxide, the reaction proceeded smoothly and the yields were better. As the manipulative details are identical in both the cases, the oxidation with hydrogen peroxide only has been described in detail.

EXPERIMENTAL.

To an alcoholic solution of *S*-methylthiosemicarbazide hydriodide (Freund and Paradies, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3114), the calculated amount of benzaldehyde was added and warmed. The condensation was followed by an immediate change of colour of the solution to yellow. The benzylidene derivative could not be isolated in a pure state.

5-Phenyl-3-methylthiol-1:2:4-triazole.—To the above solution, a little more than the calculated quantity of perhydrol diluted with ten times its volume of a mixture of alcohol and water (1:1) was added drop by drop through an upright condenser, with continuous shaking. The mixture was then boiled on the water-bath for about three minutes. The solution turned red and a tarry substance separated out. On passing steam through the mixture, the tar solidified; this was then repeatedly recrystallised from a mixture of alcohol and water (1:1) in white plates, m.p. 164°. (Found: C, 56.77; H, 4.89; N, 22.10. $C_9H_9N_3S$ requires C, 56.54; H, 4.71; N, 21.99 per cent.).

5-Phenyl-3-ethylthiol-1:2:4-triazole.—It was prepared in a similar way. Crystallised from dilute alcohol, it melted at 166°. (Found: N, 20.62. $C_{10}H_{11}N_3S$ requires N, 20.49 per cent.).

Benzylidene-S-methyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone.—A mixture of equimolecular quantities of 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide and methyl iodide was boiled in alcoholic solution for 15 minutes under reflux. One molecule of benzaldehyde was added and warmed. The deep yellow solution soon deposited pale yellow crystals which were recrystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 153°. This is the hydriodide of benzylidene-S-methyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone, which is hydrolysed by boiling water. On treatment with moderately strong ammonia, the free base was precipitated as a pale yellow mass. This was collected, dried on a porous plate and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 66-67°. (Found: N, 15.59. $C_{15}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 15.61 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* was obtained by shaking an absolute alcoholic solution of the substance with fuming hydrochloride acid.

4:5-Diphenyl-3-methylthiol-1:2:4-triazole.—An alcoholic solution of the above benzylidene-S-methyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone was treated with hydrogen peroxide as before. The mixture was boiled for 5 minutes and left overnight. Next day the crystals, which separated out along with a little tar, were collected pressed on a porous tile and twice crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 165-66°. (Found: N, 16.00. $C_{15}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 15.73 per cent.).

The *hydriodide of benzylidene-S-ethyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone* was prepared in the same way as the methyl derivative and had m.p. 116°. The free base crystallised from alcohol and melted at 78°. (Found: N, 14.93. $C_{10}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 14.84 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* crystallised from absolute alcohol and melted at 178° (decomp.).

4:5-Diphenyl-3-ethylthiol-1:2:4-triazole.—It was obtained by the oxidation of the above benzylidene compound, by means of perhydrol or ferric chloride. It crystallised from 50 per cent. alcohol as white needles, m.p. 148°. (Found: N, 15.07. $C_{15}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 14.95 per cent.). No tar was formed during oxidation with perhydrol.

Benzylidene-S-methyl-4-o-tolylthiosemicarbazone.—The hydride was prepared in the usual manner, and crystallised from rectified spirit; m.p. 189° (decomp.). The free base crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 62°. (Found: N, 14.95. $C_{16}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 14.84 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* crystallised from absolute alcohol; m.p. 194° (decomp.).

4-o-Tolyl-5-phenyl-3-methylthiol-1:2:4-triazole.—After oxidation in the usual way by hydrogen peroxide or ferric chloride a dark coloured solution was obtained. No solid separated out during 3 days. Steam was then passed through the solution, when a semi-solid mass, which hardened on cooling was obtained. A small quantity of crystals was also obtained from the aqueous portion. These were crystallised from alcohol (charcoal); m.p. 130°. (Found: N, 15.08. $C_{16}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 14.95 per cent.).

4-o-Tolyl-5-phenyl-3-ethylthiol-1:2:4-triazole.—The hydriodide of benzylidene-*S*-ethylthiosemicarbazone, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from rectified spirit; m.p. 123°. The free base was an oily substance which did not solidify. The *hydrochloride* melted at 167°.

Considerable quantities of tar were formed during oxidation, although it was conducted with great care. The crystals that came out from the aqueous portion were collected after a few hours and thrice crystallised from very dilute alcohol as silky needles, m.p. 107°. (Found: N, 14.33. $C_{17}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 14.24 per cent.).

Benzylidene-S-methyl-4-p-tolylthiosemicarbazone.—The hydride separated from rectified spirit; m.p. 180° (decomp.). The free base crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 71°. (Found: N, 14.96. $C_{16}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 14.84 per cent.). The *hydrochloride* melted at 130° (decomp.).

4-p-Tolyl-5-phenyl-3-methylthiol-1:2:4-triazole.—The free base was oxidised in the usual manner. On steaming the reaction products, the tar solidified. This was twice crystallised from dilute alcohol; m.p. 176°. (Found: N, 15.06. $C_{16}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 14.95 per cent.).

Benzylidene-S-ethyl-4-p-tolylthiosemicarbazone.—The hydroiodide crystallised from rectified spirit; m.p. 165°. The free base was a semi-solid mass which did not solidify even on long standing. The hydrochloride crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 158°.

4-p-Tolyl-5-phenyl-3-ethylthiol-1:2:4-triazole.—It formed silky white needles from alcohol; m.p. 148°. (Found: C, 68.79; H, 5.97; N, 14.54. $C_{17}H_{17}N_3S$ requires C, 69.15; H, 5.76; N, 14.24 per cent.).

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Reviews

Ausführung quantitativer Analysen: (The Practice of Quantitative Analysis) by H. Biltz and W. Biltz with 49 figures. *Royal Soc.*, 400 pages. Published by Verlag von S. Hirzel in Leipzig C. 1, 1930.

This book gives instructions on quantitative analysis of inorganic substances. The introductory portion is devoted to the description of various manipulative analytical practices and other preliminary directions.

The book then deals with the gravimetric and volumetric estimation of individual elements discussing the theoretical principles underlying the different methods wherever it is necessary. Almost all the important recently developed methods of estimation as well as the electroanalytical methods and potentiometric titrations are included here.

The method of conductometric titration however is very summarily dealt with in a single page (p. 199) with general remarks without any details regarding the actual practice as applied to any concrete instance.

Then follows several chapters giving descriptions of processes for the analysis of various minerals, preparations, manures, pigments, alloys, steel, coal, coke, large varieties of ores foundry products, silicates including glasses. A short course of water analysis has also been included. These cover more than half the bulk of the book. The theoretical principles dealing with the methods of quantitative separation have been discussed in each individual case. One however misses here the minerals containing certain rarer elements like niobium, tantalum, beryllium, zirconium, thorium and the rare-earths. The addition of processes for the analysis of a few minerals like columbite, beryl, monazite, zircon, etc. would however have completed the course.

The descriptions of methods given in the book are lucid and condensed. Sources of probable error have also been indicated in each individual case. As most of the methods dealt with in this book have actually been tested in the authors' laboratories, the book

possesses a special importance of its own and will undoubtedly be of great practical help to the analytical workers. All unnecessary details, old and less reliable methods have been more or less excluded. A chapter on gas analysis which at present is wanting would have been welcome by many analysts.

One would however like to see the addition of some more improved methods of separation, *e.g.*, Lundell's method of separation of the ammonia group of elements from those of the ammonium sulphide group by ammonia in presence of an indicator, and also that based on the use of hexamine for the same purpose. These two recent methods have been found to possess decided advantages over the classical acetate method.

On the whole the book is a valuable addition to our existing standard text-books on analytical chemistry and can be commended as well to the beginners and advanced students as to the teachers on analytical chemistry. Tables of atomic weights, chemical factors and logarithms if annexed at the end would have been much appreciated by all workers. An English edition of the book will be welcome to the English speaking students and workers. The binding and printing of the book are quite good.

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